

INFLUENCE OF STRAIN RATE AND TEMPERATURE ON THE IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF POLYETHYLENE FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

A.A.J.M. Peijs, E.A.M. Smets and L.E. Govaert
Centre for Polymers and Composites
Eindhoven University of Technology
5600 MB Eindhoven, The Netherlands

ABSTRACT

The influence of strain rate and temperature on modulus, strength and work of fracture of high-performance polyethylene (HP-PE) fibres and composites is investigated. Results showed that an increase in strain rate and/or decrease in temperature leads to a reduction in work of fracture. At high strain rates or low temperatures a constant minimum level for fracture energy is reached. The energy absorption capacity of HP-PE/epoxy laminates is investigated using full penetrating dart-impact tests and showed similar trends than observed for HP-PE fibres. The impact energy of these laminates could be quantitatively described in terms of fibre, matrix and delamination effects by combining the tensile test results on fibres and composites with mode I fracture toughness experiments on laminates.

Keywords: polyethylene fibre, epoxy, strain rate, temperature, impact, energy absorption.

1. INTRODUCTION

High-performance polyethylene fibres (HP-PE) are currently produced by solution (gel) spinning of ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMW-PE) and possess unique mechanical properties in terms of high specific strength and stiffness [1]. Moreover, these HP-PE fibres possess a relatively high work-to-break -i.e., good impact properties- compared with carbon, aramid and glass fibres. Due to these unique properties HP-PE fibres have a high potential for use in impact resistant and ballistic composites. Because of relatively poor structural properties of HP-PE composites, especially hybridization with other high performance fibres such as carbon [2] or aramid [3] offers interesting possibilities for combining structural performance with impact resistance. However, since viscoelastic fibres such as HP-PE possess a strong time and temperature dependent behaviour this also implies that the fracture energy of these fibres and impact behaviour of its composites will display a pronounced strain rate and temperature dependence.

Previous studies on the time dependent behaviour of HP-PE fibres has shown that the deformation of these fibres can be considered to be the resultant of two simultaneous contributions [3,4]. First, a reversible (viscoelastic) process which dominates at short loading times, low temperatures and/or low stress levels and secondly, a non-linear plastic flow contribution which becomes more pronounced at longer times, high temperatures

and/or high stress levels (plateau creep). Studies on strain rate effects in HP-PE fibres by Prevorsek et al. [5], claimed an increase in modulus at strain rates above approximately 10^3 min^{-1} . In this study, fibres were tested using high speed transverse ballistic impact testing of HP-PE fibres. The authors claim that at deformation rates exceeding 10^5 min^{-1} the modulus of HP-PE fibres (Spectra® 1000) becomes insensitive to strain rate changes. However, since the reported values for moduli (up to 320 GPa) even exceeds the modulus of a polyethylene single crystal (235 GPa) [6], -i.e., being the maximum attainable modulus for polyethylene- these values are rather questionable. Research on the influence of strain rate [7] and temperature [8] on the strength of HP-PE fibres showed a decrease in strength and a transition from (pseudo) brittle fracture to yielding with decreasing strain rates and/or increasing temperatures.

The influence of test temperature on the impact performance of composite laminates has been reported by Zimmerman et al. [9]. They conducted full penetrating drop weight impact tests, at three different temperatures, on laminates incorporating two types of HP-PE (Spectra® 900 and 1000), aramid (Kevlar® 49) and E-glass fibre and observed for HP-PE laminates an enhanced energy absorption capacity with increasing temperature.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The HP-PE fibre used in this study was Dyneema® SK 60 supplied by DSM High Performance Fibers bv. A common epoxy system (Araldite LY 556/HY 917/ DY 070) was used as the principle matrix for the fabrication of composites.

Cross-ply laminated plates with a thickness of 1.3 mm (45 vol.% fibre) were manufactured by stacking three plies of pre-impregnated woven fabric (plain weave, 200 gm^{-2}) in a [0,90] lay-up in a mould. Laminates were cured for 4 h under combined vacuum and pressure conditions in a press-clave at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and subsequently post-cured for 12 h at $110 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

2.2 Testing

Tensile tests on HP-PE yarn (400 den) with a length of 200 mm were performed on a Zwick 1445 tensile tester equipped with a thermostatically controlled oven and pneumatic fibre-clamps. Static mechanical experiments were conducted at different strain rates (10^{-5} to 10^{-1} s^{-1}) and different temperatures ($-40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

Impact performance of laminated plates was measured using an instrumented dart-test on a Zwick Rel tensile machine at different temperatures ($-40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and different impact speeds (0.004 ms^{-1} to 5 ms^{-1}). Laminated plates ($60 \times 60 \text{ mm}$) were clamped between two plates with an internal diameter of 20 mm. A hemispherical dart with a diameter of 10 mm was used and impact energies were obtained by recording the load-time curve during penetration.

3. FIBRE CHARACTERIZATION

3.1 Modulus

To a first approximation HP-PE fibres can be regarded to be linear viscoelastic in dynamic and/or short-term loading situations as encountered in impact situations. Since this study

focuses on short-term loading situations, the contribution of the plastic deformation process can be neglected. For a linear viscoelastic material, the Boltzmann superposition principle applied to uniaxial extension yields:

$$\sigma = \int_0^t E(t-t') \dot{\epsilon}(t') dt' \quad (1)$$

This convolution integral provides a mathematical equation that relates viscoelastic stress to strain under various loading conditions. The time dependent behaviour is characterized by a viscoelastic function, in this case the stress relaxation modulus $E(t)$. Well-known characterization methods for linear viscoelastic materials, that cover a sufficient wide time-frequency range, are dynamic excitation, creep or stress-relaxation experiments. Although all these methods can be successfully applied to the characterization of HP-PE [3,4], an alternative approach, using conventional tensile tests at different strain rates and temperatures, has been followed in this study. In the case of linear viscoelastic behaviour, it can easily be deduced that:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \epsilon} = E \left(t = \frac{\epsilon}{\dot{\epsilon}} \right) \quad (2)$$

This implies that values for the relaxation modulus $E(t)$ can simply be determined from tangent-moduli at a fixed strain level. In order to cover a sufficient wide time-frequency range, tensile experiments were performed at strain rates which varied from 10^{-5} to 10^{-1} s^{-1} and temperatures ranging from $-40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. From all these stress-strain curves secant-moduli at 1% strain were calculated which were subsequently transferred into isotherms for the stress relaxation modulus. A master curve for the modulus at $23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, constructed by horizontal shifting and matching of these isotherms, is presented in Figure 1. Since time-temperature superposition is valid for HP-PE fibres [4], master curves obtained in this way can be used to predict the actual fibre behaviour over a large times scale. The temperature dependence can be described with a thermally activated Arrhenius process with an activation energy of 27 kcalmol^{-1} .

Figure 1. Mastercurve for modulus of HP-PE fibre at RT as function of loading time.

3.2 Strength

Isotherms for the failure strength of HP-PE yarn are constructed from tensile experiments at different temperatures and strain rates. From Figure 2 it can be seen that an increase in temperature leads to a decrease in strength or yield stress. Yielding was observed in the case of extremely low strain rates and/or high temperatures. A master curve for the strength of HP-PE fibres at 23 °C is constructed by horizontal shifting of these isotherms (Figure 3). From this master curve it can be concluded that even at room temperature (RT), yielding occurs at low strain rates ($< 4 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Also in this case the behaviour can be described by one single thermally activated process. The calculated activation energy for this process (20 kcalmol^{-1}) is comparable to that for the reversible deformation process.

Figure 2. Fibre strength as a function of strain rate at different temperatures.

Figure 3. Master curve for fibre strength at RT.

3.3 Work of fracture

The work of fracture of the HP-PE fibres is calculated from the experimental data by integration of the area under the stress-strain curves. Since the stress-strain behaviour, as well as the failure stress of the fibre is fully characterized, work of fracture can be predicted using:

$$U(\epsilon) = \int_0^{\epsilon_b} \sigma(\epsilon) d\epsilon \quad (3)$$

where ϵ_b is the failure strain and $\sigma(\epsilon)$ can be calculated for different strains using equation (2) since the relaxation modulus $E(t)$ is known (Figure 1). The strain at break is predicted by combining the predicted $\sigma(\epsilon)$ and the strain rate dependence of the strength. The drawn line in Figure 4 shows the predictions for the work of fracture at RT. Numerical predictions are in good agreement with experimental data, indicating the validity of the model. Work of fracture for HP-PE fibres decreases with increasing strain rate and results in a constant minimum fracture energy of approximately 30 Jcm^{-3} .

Figure 4. Work of fracture versus strain rate for fibres: (●) experiment, (—) predicted.

4. IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Energy absorption during impact of laminated plates was determined from the load-time curves. Figure 5 shows the isotherms for impact energy of HP-PE/epoxy laminates. From this graph it can be concluded that the penetration energy increases with increasing temperature. Similar to the interpretation of the results on HP-PE fibres, also here the isotherms are horizontally shifted in order to construct a mastercurve for the impact energy at RT (Figure 6).

Figure 5. Total impact energy as a function of impact speed at different temperatures.

Figure 6. Master curve for impact energy at RT.

5. ENERGY ABSORPTION MECHANISMS

5.1 Fibre fracture

By considering the energy absorption per unit volume a correlation can be made between the work of fracture of HP-PE fibres and the impact energy of HP-PE/epoxy laminates. The volume of fibre in a fabric [0,90] laminate which will be loaded in tension in a dart-impact test and which is available for energy absorption by fibre fracture is a cross with arms of 10 mm width and 20 mm length. The effective fibre volume can be calculated by:

$$V_{fibre} = 2 [d * d_i * h * V_f * 0.5] \quad (4)$$

where d is the free test length (20 mm), d_i is the dart diameter (10 mm), h is thickness of laminate (1.3 mm) and V_f is the volume fraction of fibre (0.45). The factor 0.5 is a cross-ply correction factor for fibre volume fraction since in a cross-ply laminate only 50% of the fibres is loaded in fibre direction. The factor 2 originates from the fact that in a fabric or cross-ply laminate, fibres will be loaded in tension in two directions. In order to correlate the tensile experiments on HP-PE fibres with the dart-impact experiments on laminated plates, besides the determination of effectively loaded fibre volumes, strain rates must be related to impact speeds. Since both the failure strains of the HP-PE fibre as well as time to failure in a dart-impact test are known, a direct correlation can easily be made between strain rate and impact speed.

5.2 Fibre fracture in composite

Tensile tests on impregnated strands (1200 den, 45 vol.% of fibre) were performed at three different temperatures (-40, 23, 40 °C) and strain rates varying from 5.10^{-4} to 10^{-1} s^{-1} in order to investigate the influence of the matrix on the fracture energy of HP-PE fibres. Fracture mechanisms in UD-composites such as fibre/matrix debonding, fibre pull-out, stress redistribution due to fibre fracture and multiple fibre fracture can result in synergy in work of fracture i.e., the work of fracture of the composite is more than the sum of the fracture energies of its constituents.

Results indicate that the stress-strain behaviour of the impregnated strands, when normalized for the volume fraction of fibre, are identical to those of the fibres tested in air. However, after impregnation an increase in strength was observed of approximately 20%. This increase in strength is the result of redistribution of stresses after fibre fracture, resulting in cumulative weakening of the composite. This increase in strength can be described in a quantitative manner with the aid of statistical models [10]. Due to the increase in fibre strength when embedded in a matrix, an increase in work of fracture is obtained of approximately 50% (Figure 7).

5.3 Delaminations

Besides energy absorption by fibre fracture in the composite, energy will also be absorbed by the formation of delaminations. An estimate of the energy which will be absorbed by delaminations can be made by multiplying the total delaminated area (= visual delaminated area x number of delaminations) with the energy necessary to create an interlaminar crack.

Under normal impact conditions -i.e., impact speed higher than 1 ms^{-1} - the delaminated

area, determined by visual observations and ultrasonic C-scan corresponds with the circular free test area ($d = 20$ mm). Therefore in a 3-ply laminate, two circular delaminations with a diameter of 20 mm are formed. In order to estimate the energy absorbed by these delaminations, mode I interlaminar fracture toughness experiments were performed on HP-PE fabric composites yielding an average value for G_{Ic} of 1.14 KJm^{-2} .

5.4 Correlation between fracture energy of fibre and composite

In Figure 7 all normalized energy absorption processes are plotted in one graph. The experimental data corresponds with the dart-impact results and are directly taken from Figure 6. The contribution of fibre fracture, in air and in a composite, is calculated from the work of fracture per unit volume of fibre multiplied by the fibre volume which is loaded in tension in the fabric composite (equation 4). Comparison of results show that dart-impact energies at high impact speeds approaches the values for work of fracture for HP-PE fibres in a composite, whereas fracture energies for HP-PE fibres when tested in air underestimate the energy absorption in composites. If we assume the delamination energy to be constant, the contribution of delaminations to the total energy absorption is approximately 0.7 J. If we take this delamination energy into account, impact energies at normal impact speeds are quantitatively described and can be considered as the sum of energy absorption by fibre fracture (90%) and energy absorption by the formation of delaminations (10%). At low 'impact' speeds the predictions based on fibre fracture and delamination are too low, indicating that at low impact speeds the role of the delamination energy is more pronounced. Since the influence of test rate and temperature on delamination energy was not investigated, this effect is not further quantified.

Figure 7. Comparison of dart-impact energy with normalized energy absorption mechanisms from (a) fibre fracture in air (b) fibre fracture in composite and (c) delaminations.

CONCLUSIONS

- A mathematical model has been developed and validated for the prediction of the work of fracture of HP-PE fibres.
- An increase in strain rate and/or a decrease in temperature results in:
 - an increase in fibre modulus
 - an increase in fibre strength
 - a decrease in work of fracture of the HP-PE fibres
 - a transition from yielding to brittle failure of the fibres
- The work of fracture of impregnated HP-PE fibres is approximately 50% higher than that of HP-PE fibres when tested in air.
- An increase in impact speed and/or a decrease in temperature results in a decrease in impact resistance of HP-PE/epoxy laminates.
- The impact resistance of HP-PE/epoxy laminates is mainly controlled by the work of fracture of the HP-PE fibres.

REFERENCES

1. Lemstra, P.J. Kirschbaum, R., Ohta, T. and Yasuda, H. in: *Developments in Oriented Polymers-2*, Ward I.M. (ed), Elsevier Appl Sci Publ, 1987, pp. 39-77.
2. Peijs, A.A.J.M., Venderbosch, R.W. and Lemstra, P.J., *Hybrid Composites based on Polyethylene and Carbon Fibres - Part 3*, Composites, 21 (6), 1990, pp. 522-530.
3. Govaert, L.E., d'Hooghe, E. and Peijs, A.A.J.M., *A Micromechanical approach to Viscoelasticity of Unidirectional Composites*, Composites, 22 (2) 1991, pp 113-119.
4. Govaert, L.E., Bastiaansen, C.W.M. and Leblans, P.J.R., *Stress Strain Analysis of Oriented Polyethylene*, Polymer, 34 (3), 1993.
5. Prevorsek, D.C., Chin, H.B. and Kwon, Y.D., *Deformation Analysis of Composites Exhibiting Large Strain-Rate Effects*, in: Composite Structures - 6, Marshall, I.H. (ed), Elsevier Appl Sci, London, 1991, pp. 617-626.
6. Nakamae, K. and Nishino, T., *Crystal Moduli of Polymers and Their Temperature Dependence*, in: Integration of Fundamental Polymer Science and Technology - 5, Lemstra, P.J. and Kleintjes L.A. (ed), Elsevier Appl Sci Publ, 1991, pp. 121-130.
7. Bastiaansen, C.W.M., *PhD Thesis*, Eindhoven University of Technology, The Netherlands, 1991.
8. Dessain, B., Moolaert, O., Keunings, R. and Bunsell, A.R., *Solid Phase Changes Controlling the Tensile and Creep Behaviour of Gel-Spun High-Modulus Polyethylene Fibres*, Journal of Material Science, 27, 1992, pp. 4515-4522.
9. Zimmerman, R.S. and Adams, D.F., *Impact Performance of Various Fibre Reinforced Composites as a Function of Temperature*, Proc. 32nd. International SAMPE Symposium, April 6-9, 1987, pp. 1461-1471.
10. Kok, J.M.M. de, Rijdsdijk, H.A. and Peijs, A.A.J.M., *Influence of the Interface on the Longitudinal Tensile Strength of Polyethylene Fibre Reinforced Composites*, in: Verpoest, I. and Jones, F. (ed.), Interfacial Phenomena '91, Butterworth-Heinemann, 1991, pp. 263-264.